

BOOKS ABOUT DESIGN AND EMOTION. FROM THE BIAS OF BRAZILIAN AUTHORSHIP AND TRANSLATION INTO PORTUGUESE

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ABSTRACT

In order to understand the development of the field of Design and Emotion in Brazil, this article presents books published by Brazilian authors and those which were translated into Portuguese. This information can guide Brazilian authors, editors and researchers to find gaps in this area to write about different issues to complement the knowledge about the use of human factors in Design.

Keywords: design, emotion, books, Brazil, Portuguese

INTRODUCTION

In January 2012, occurred the *First Brazilian Seminar on Design and Emotion* in Porto Alegre, Brazil. This event showed the great interest that the community of designers in southern Brazil has about the use of human factors in the design process.

At least 180 people attended to the event including teachers, graduate and undergraduate students and professionals. It was important to introduce some aspects that people might know about this theoretical field, such as what designing oriented to emotion is and its main approaches; some examples of experiences in this area; and what is being researched in Design and Emotion field (Design and Emotion, 2012).

Aiming to map the researches on Design and Emotion in Brazil, this paper will present the books published by Brazilian authors and editors and books translated into Portuguese. It is important to know the

publications on the home bias of its authors or editors, because they spread the knowledge in their regions or research group. The fact of having publications in your language, in this case, in Portuguese, certainly helps those who wish to start a search in a field of knowledge. This information is also useful because it can guide Brazilian authors and editors to find gaps to research and write about different issues on Design and Emotion.

BRAZILIAN AUTHORS

The Brazilian authored books found are shown in Table 1:

Year	Title of the book	Author/Editor
2006	O Poder do Design: da Ostentação à Emoção - The Power of Design: the ostentation to Emotion	Katia Faggiani
2007	Ergonomia e Design: prazer conforto e risco no uso de produtos - Ergonomics and Design, pleasure, comfort and risk in the use of products	Júlio Carlos de Souza van der Linden
2008	Design Ergonomia Emoção - Design Ergonomics Emotion	Vera Damazio e Cláudia Mont'alvão (editors)
2010	Shoes, cars, and other love stories: Investigating the experience of love for products	Beatriz Russo

Table 1. Brazilian authored books

Faggiani (2006) in her book *O Poder do Design* (The Power of Design) talks about the relationship of Design to the production of luxury goods, seeking to understand how Design affects the choices in Brazilian consumers and contributes to the increase the exportation of these products. The author was graduated in Industrial Design at the Universidade de Brasília (UNB), with a Master Degree in Design at Pontifícia Universidade Católica do Rio de Janeiro (PUC-Rio) and Ph.D. in Management/Marketing in Lisbon University Institute (Faggiani, 2011).

Since the book *Ergonomia e Design: prazer conforto e risco no uso de produtos* (Ergonomics and Design, pleasure, comfort and risk in the use of products), from Julio van der Linden (2007), results from his doctoral thesis in the area of Production Engineering at Universidade Federal Rio Grande do Sul (UFRGS). Julio has a degree in Design from the Universidade Federal de Pernambuco (UFPE) and Master, Doctoral and Postdoctoral studies at the Programa de Pós-Graduação em Engenharia de Produção at UFRGS. He is currently teaching in undergraduate and graduate courses in Design at the same institution (van der Linden, 2011).

Design Ergonomia Emoção (Design Ergonomics Emotion) is a collection of articles organized by Vera Damazio and Claudia Mont'alvão. Vera is a professor and coordinator of the *Laboratório Design Memória e Emoção – LABMEMO* (Design, Memory and Emotion Laboratory) at PUC-Rio and its research links Emotional Design with humor, citizenship, changing habits and behavior, sociability, self-esteem and well-being (Damazio, 2011). Claudia, besides teaching, coordinates the *Laboratório de Ergonomia e Usabilidade de Interfaces (LEUI)* at PUC-Rio (Mont'alvão, 2011). *Design Ergonomics Emotion* has six articles showing mainly studies developed by Brazilian researchers at PUC-Rio, UFRGS, Universidade Estadual do Rio de Janeiro (UERJ) and

at Universidade Federal de Campina Grande. In addition, two articles are a partnership with researchers from other countries, from University for the Creative Arts in England and from Delft University of Technology, in Netherlands. The last one has the title *Sobre amar um Produto: Os princípios fundamentais* (About Love a Product: The Fundamental Principles) was written by Beatriz Russo along with Paul Hekkert, one of the creators of Design and Emotion Society (Damazio and Mont'alvão, 2008).

In 2010 through Beatriz Russo's book *Shoes, cars, and other love stories: Investigating the experience of love for products*, we can see the power that emotions can have when the designer knows how to use it well. Beatriz developed special tools to analyze how the interactions from person-product are linked to the love experience, and how this love can influence the user over time. She was graduated in Industrial Design at the Faculdade da Cidade and in Human Factors, Applied Ergonomics and Industrial Design at PUC-Rio. She has Master Degree in Ergonomics at the same institution, Specialization in Ergonomics in Work Spaces also in PUC-Rio and PhD in Design and Experience at Delft University of Technology. Her book *Shoes, cars, and other love stories: Investigating the experience of love for products* resulted from her PhD in Delft University of Technology. Although the author is a Brazilian, the book is available only in English.

The few publications from Brazilian authors may be related to what van der Linden (2010) expounds on his studies about Design researches in Brazil, which was only institutionalized in the academic environment of post-graduate studies in 1990. Therefore, if the Design studies are still new in the country, researches focused on emotional factors are more recent in relation to the international scene.

BOOKS TRANSLATED INTO PORTUGUESE

It has been found only three books translated into Brazilian Portuguese, as we can see in Table 2:

Year	Title	Author
1986	<i>Objects of Desire: Design and Society Since 1750</i>	Adrian Forty
2008	Objetos de Desejo: Design e Sociedade desde 1750	
2004	<i>Emotional Design: Why We Love (or Hate) Everyday Things</i>	Donald Norman
2008	Design Emocional: por que adoramos (ou detestamos) os objetos do dia-a-dia	
2006	<i>Brandjam: Humanizing Brands Through Emotional Design</i>	Marc Gobé
2010	Brandjam: o design emocional na humanização das marcas	

Table 2. Publications translated into Portuguese (Brazil).

Adrian Forty's book, first published in 1986 in English, is only released in Brazil in 2008, reprinted in 2010. The book is about how societies express their values through the social and economic design. Forty is a professor of The Bartlett School of Architecture at University College London (Forty, 2010).

One of the most cited books was written by Donald Norman, *Emotional Design* (2004), which was released in Portuguese version in 2008. To understand why we love (or hate) the objects of day-to-day, Donald has a theoretical basis, addressing three types of design: visceral, behavioral and reflective (Norman, 2008).

The book by Marc Gobé, *Brandjam: Humanizing Brands Through Emotional Design*, which was launched in 2006, has its translation into Portuguese in 2010. Marc specializes in branding and proposes to build a brand relationship with consumers, and for this to occur it is necessary to integrate all working on the project as well as marketing professionals in the

integration of these unique sensory experiences (Gobé, 2010).

The information gathered leads to believe that the publication of books in Portuguese is recent, since 2008. This lack of publication in the Brazilian language may have been impaired or delayed the spread of the inclusion of emotional factors in Design in Brazil. Therefore, it is necessary to resort to publications in other languages, which are mostly in English, once there is a deficient supply of books in Portuguese.

CONCLUSIONS

This work showed the books authored by Brazilians and books translated into Portuguese. The lack of publications may have occurred due to the late development of research on emotional factors applied to the design in Brazil.

The fact that there are a few books translated into Portuguese restricted the view that readers have from the scope of the field of Design and Emotion.

It is hoped that this work can help Brazilian researchers to perceive a lack of research in this field. And to people who are interested in the subject can know a little about the history of research of the authors and editors of books in this area.

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